

Real Time Multi-Object Detection and Distance Estimation Based on YOLO8 Using Webcam

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Abstract

An essential component of automated driving technology is vehicle movement estimation. It is essential for detection, distance estimation, and rear-end collision avoidance. This paper presents a technique for calculating vehicle distances on highways and in downtown areas. One of the most traditional deep learning challenges is distance estimation using a camera. Based on multi-object detection and machine learning approaches, this paper proposes an algorithm for determining the distance from a camera to an object. The first step of the algorithm is to collect various object types of images and calculate real-time distances between them and the camera. Following that, the YOLOv8 algorithm detects each object in a video stream and generates bounding boxes for each one. Testing results show that YOLOv8n has a detection accuracy of 99.5% mAP (mean average precision)- the efficient and precise results of object detection and distance estimation on a trained dataset. The distance estimation of multi-objects for the same distance, the root mean square error (RSME), is about 3.5% on average. For the difference distance of multi-objects, the RMSE is about 3.12% and 2.3% on average. Conclusively, the suggested method can determine the estimated distance with minimal error rate between a camera and multiple objects.

Keywords: *deep learning, YOLOv8 deep neural network, object detection, distance estimation, and real time video.*

Suggested citation: Aunga, Y.Y., Lwinb, M.M., & Pradhan, D. (2025). Real Time Multi-Object Detection and Distance Estimation Based on YOLO8 Using Webcam. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 2(1), 55-67. DOI: 10.59324/stss.2025.2(1).05

Introduction

Within eight months, there were 106 accidents on the Yangon-Mandalay Expressway, according to the Expressway Police Force Office. Four-wheeled vehicles are involved in some incidents, and express cars follow. Rear-end crashes occur because of human error, such as when a motorist is too tired to judge another driver's speed or distance. The estimation of the distance between cars is a crucial topic in autonomous cars. Thus, accurately detecting information about surrounding vehicles (e.g., the distance between them) in real-time is a challenging but important problem. Autonomous vehicles must be able to recognize other vehicles, regardless of their form or nature, according to Abdellatif et al. (2019). As a result, some algorithms, including those for vehicle

detection and distance and speed estimation, should be used. According to Puguh Budi et al. (2019), automated cars use the information that is extracted using these algorithms to make judgments, such as modifying their speed or path or avoiding other vehicles.

J. Shashirangana et al. (2021) state that edge detection is part of a typical license plate detection algorithm that selects relevant license plates from areas with a high character density. However, that is untrue. A. S. Mohammed Shariff et al. (2021) claim that while deep learning OCR methods like Tesseract can be computationally demanding and imprecise with distorted images, neural networks offer an advantage by processing raw pixel data directly. OCR systems find widespread application. Character segmentation is frequently the first step in these systems' classification process, which is followed by feature extraction or template-matching techniques. S. S. Patil et al. (2023) claim that YOLOv8 models have a high degree of accuracy. EasyOCR and YOLOv8 together bring us remarkable accuracy and efficiency in character detection.

To improve system accuracy, Nurnajmin et al.'s stereo-vision-based distance estimation method Ann, et al. (2018) makes use of a unique image template matching technique. The distance measurement problem was more successfully resolved when they used the simulated Kalman filter (SKF) technique for template matching. An innovative driving assistance system was put into place by Ahmad Alfi et al. to identify objects and evaluate their distance. With a mean average precision of 75%, the MobileNetV2 architecture received the highest score in the object detection experiment test utilizing the KITTI and PASCAL datasets (Adz-Dzikri, et al., 2021).

The focal length, the separation between the cameras, and the differences in the images taken by the two cameras, among other technical information, may all be used to compute the distance, claim Mrovlje et al. (2008) In Mrovlje, & Vrancic, (2008), the researcher discovered that the best accuracy for classifying distance ranges was 96.28% for automobile photos and 94.57% for motorcycle images, while the lowest error for estimating the distance in meters was 0.47 m for car images and 0.62 m for motorcycle images. The camera-based method is widely used for object recognition in blind spot areas due to its low cost and excellent accuracy, according to recent research (Zhao, et al., 2019; Kwon, et al., 2019). However, the picture from a monocular camera is unable to show how far away the camera is.

However, the image captured by a monocular camera is unable to directly display the distance between the camera and the object. Three contributions came from Rais Bastomi et al.'s paper: (1) it defined object detection as a regression problem for the environment around the user; (2) it combined CNN with stereo vision for object detection and object measurement; and (3) it generated sound based on the classified and distance-measured objects. According to test results, this gadget could detect specified objects such as humans, tables, chairs, cars, bicycles, and motorbikes with an average accuracy of 93.33%. For distances between 50 and 300 cm, the measurement error was roughly 6.1% (Bastomi, et al., 2019).

Using a simple mathematical model, indirect distance is measured with a digital camera and monocular vision Bui, et al. (2017), Bui, Doskocil, & Krivanek, (2018), and Bui, et al., (2019). This model is used to calculate the indirect distance measurement error and variability. The precision of the measurement is further assessed by considering the impact of multiple components, including the object's width, distance, and camera specifications (such as focal length, sensor size, and resolution), on the measurement results.

Deep convolutional neural networks have greatly enhanced the ability to detect visual objects (CNN). An individual GPU (Liu, et al., 2015), Redmon, & Farhadi, (2016) can process a few frames per second using the substantially enhanced Faster R-CNN (Ren, et al., 2015). Regular smartphones and other low-power devices cannot use the Faster RCNN because to its processing expense. In comparison, SSD (Fan, Brown, & Smith, 2016) and YOLO (Girshick, et al., 2014) are significantly

faster than Ren, et al., (2015), Girshick, (2015), and Shinde, Kothari, & Gupta, (2018) since they identify objects in a single step. In specifics, a NVidia Titan-X GPU is used by the SSD to analyze 59 images per second (FPS) from the PASCAL VOC 2007 dataset with a mAP of 74.3%.

The research paper's primary focus will be on preventing rear-end collisions. The suggested solution reduces rear-end collisions, which are primarily caused by drivers misjudging the speed and distance of another vehicle, by using a webcam installed on the dashboard of the car to measure the distance of multiple objects. The suggested approach consists of two steps: determining the multi-object's distance and identifying it on the camera. The first and last phases of effectively estimating distance and accurately detecting multiple objects are approached by this proposed system.

Methodology

The dataset used in this paper was created using camera-captured images from city roads. The Python and YOLOv8 computer languages were used throughout the whole computational development process on Google Colab instances. These instances have CUDA 11.2 loaded, an NVIDIA Tesla T4 GPU, 8GB of RAM, and a Core i5-10300H CPU running at 2.50GHz.

The diagram in Figure 1 displays the workflow as well as every development stage.

Figure 1. The Workflow of Multi-Object Detection and Distance Estimation

Initially, a webcam was used to record videos of the automobiles on the city road. Following that, frame extraction and manual annotation of the bounding boxes surrounding the objects of the different classes were carried out. The YOLOv8 model's architecture was trained and validated in the second phase. Thus, in order to assess the YOLOv8 models, object detection and classification were done. In the third phase, the distance between vehicles is estimated using the detection objects that are fed into the distance estimation system.

Object Detection with YOLOv8

Because YOLO processes the full image through the neural network at once, it achieves high-accuracy object detection. It operates in real time when detecting objects. The YOLO model is one type of single-stage detector that is based on a convolutional neural network (CNN). Single-stage detectors

include the SSD and YOLO versions. YOLO divides an image into grids using a single convolutional neural network and then assigns bounding boxes and confidence score predictions to each grid. The highest confidence score is used to identify the object class.

Figure 2. The YOLOv8 Model's Architecture

According to the object map pyramid experiment, in order to jointly predict YOLOv8, multiple pyramids are used to obtain the object detection results. Furthermore, additional heads can be directly connected to the pyramids in the middle layer to obtain the desired results (Ju & Cai, 2021; Terven & Cordova-Esparaza, 2023; Wang et al., 2022). A deep learning technological advancement approach called YOLOv8 has been implemented in a real-time application. Computer vision techniques were used by autonomous drive systems. Modern YOLOv8 is used to lessen the tiresome manual video stream monitoring from cameras. Object detection is an essential phase in autonomous systems.

There are three primary components that make up the YOLOv8 architecture: convolutional neural networks (CNNs) that extract features from the input image are called backbones. Utilizing a customized CSPDarknet53 backbone, YOLOv8 enhances accuracy and information flow between layers by utilizing cross-stage partial connections. In order to collect data at diverse scales, Neck, sometimes referred to as the feature extractor, combines feature maps from several backbone phases.

Instead of using the conventional Feature Pyramid Network (FPN), YOLOv8 makes use of a C2F module. This module improves detection accuracy, particularly for small objects, by combining low-level spatial information with high-level characteristics. Head: Predicting the future is the

responsibility of the head. Bounding boxes, confidence scores, and classification probabilities are predicted for every grid cell in the feature map by YOLOv8 using a number of detection modules. To get the final detections, these predictions are then added together.

Distance Estimation

Based on the principle of the camera's lens, it is possible to compute the distance between the camera and the object in the image.

Figure 3. The Camera's Working Principle

If the real width of the objects in the image is known, the distance between the camera and the objects can be calculated. A basic description of a camera's workings and the formulas used to determine distance are displayed in Figure 3. Figure 3's left side depicts a real object, while the right side shows how the image appears on camera. With point O representing the location of the camera lens, AB denoting the plane in which the object is located in the actual coordinates, and CD representing the image plane, the distance can be computed using the similarity of triangles.

Triangles that are similar to each other can be used to compute the distance between an object and the camera lens. ABO and CDO are comparable in accordance with the triangle's principle. So, it is possible to derive the following equation:

$$W:d=w:d \tag{1}$$

where W represents the object's real width, w denotes the object's width in the image, and f denotes the camera's focal length.

$$f = \frac{(w * d)}{W} \tag{2}$$

Most commonly, distance is known as a constant and has a value of d in Equation 2. One may easily compute the value of f if the detected object's value (w) is taken from an image and W is the real object's width measured.

$$d = \frac{(W * f)}{w} \tag{3}$$

where the distance between the object and the camera may be accurately calculated and determined using w and f . As a result, the proposed system uses machine learning techniques to estimate the distance between the camera and the objects that are detected.

Experimental Results and Discussion

Dataset

At 30 frames per second, the webcam recorded video on a city road with a resolution of 1080x720. To prevent selecting comparable images, a sample of 693 frames that were dispersed in time was used. 70% (475 photos), 20% (135 images), and 10% (80 images) of the sample frames were randomly selected to create the training, validation, and test sets. Cars predominate over trucks, license plates, and motorcycles in each frame, which contains multiple objects of various classifications.

Labels for object detection are annotations that contain the position of each object in the images. Bounding boxes are employed in images to divide objects. Roboflow software was utilized to perform annotations on all datasets.

Evaluation Indicators

Precision, recall, $mAP@0.5$, $mAP@0.5-0.95$, the number of model parameters, model size, and detection speed are used as evaluation metrics to test the detection performance of the suggested system-improved model. If the intersection over union (IOU) between the predicted bounding boxes and ground truth bounding boxes is larger than 0.5, the average precision (AP) for each category is represented by $mAP@0.5$ and $mAP@0.5-0.95$, respectively.

A number of the evaluation metrics that were previously discussed incorporate the following parameters into their formulas: TP (which stands for predicted positive sample and actual positive sample), FP (which stands for predicted positive sample but actual negative sample), and FN (which stands for predicted negative sample but actual positive sample). The ratio of the bounding box's and the real box's intersection and concatenation is known as the intersection over union (IoU) (Bui, Dostkocil, & Krivanek, 2018).

Precision is determined as (4): Precision is the ratio of all detected samples to the number of positive samples predicted by the model.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (4)$$

Recall is defined as the proportion of correctly predicted positive samples by the model to the total number of positive samples that were seen. Recall is calculated and shown in (5).

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (5)$$

The area under the precision-recall curve is equal to the average precision (AP), which is computed as follows (6):

$$AP = \int_0^1 \text{Precision}(\text{Recall})d(\text{Recall}) \quad (6)$$

The formula to calculate mean average precision (mAP), which is a measure of the model's detection performance across all categories, is as follows (7):

$$mAP = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n AP_i \tag{7}$$

The number of categories of the samples in the training dataset ($n = 4$) is indicated by the symbol n , and the AP_i in (7) indicates the AP value with category index value i . The average accuracy is indicated as mAP0.5 when the detection model's IoU is set to 0.5 and by mAP0.5-0.95 when it is set between 0.5 and 0.95.

Experimental Results for Object Detection

This test is detecting multi-objects that have been determined with the dataset in real-time. The images in Figures 4 and 5 are samples taken from the real-time experiments. The YOLO v8n model was used to capture images shown in Figures 4 and 5. The videos have a resolution of 1080 x 720. The test results are below.

Figure 4 The Result of Truck, Motorcycle, and License Plate Detection Uses the YOLOv8n Model with a Training Dataset

Figure 5. The Result of Car Detection Uses the YOLOv8n Model with a Training Dataset

After the training of data from our dataset using the YOLOv8 algorithm both for vehicle detection and license plate detection, the confusion matrix is shown below.

Figure 6. Confusion Matrix for Multi-Class Object Detection

Below are the box loss and mean average precision for the trained data. By averaging the AP values across several object classes, the mean average precision (mAP) expands on the idea of average precision. This is useful in multi-class object detection scenarios to provide an evaluation of the model's performance.

Figure 7. Training Process Diagram for the YOLOv8n Model

Figure 7 illustrates the training process of the YOLOv8n model on the trained dataset. Throughout each of the 25 epochs, unusual fluctuations may be observed in the training set's loss curve.

According to mAP@0.5 and mAP@0.95, the model performance metrics of YOLOv8n for multi-class are as follows in Table 1.

Table 1. Performance Result of YOLOv8n on a Trained Dataset

Model	Class	mAP0.5	mAP0.5-0.95
YOLOv8n	Truck	0.995	0.968
	Car	0.995	0.982
	License-plate	0.987	0.759
	Motorcycle	0.995	0.902

Based on the experimental results of the YOLOv8n model, the F1-score for multi-class object detection ranges from 94.8% to 99.5%, with an overall mean F1-score of 99.5%. The recall values of the multi-class object detection using YOLOv8 vary between 95.1% and 99.5%, with a mean recall of 98.9%. The precision metrics for multi-class object detection with YOLOv8 fall within the range of 95.7% to 99.8% across various categories, with an average precision of 99.7%.

Experimental Results for Distance Estimation

The evaluation of distance estimation using a training dataset will start with the metrics of absolute error, relative error, mean absolute error (MAE), mean square error (MSE), and root mean square error (RMSE). These metrics' equation is as follows:

$$\text{Absolute Error } (\Delta) = |D_A - D_M| \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Relative Error } (\%) = \left| \frac{\Delta}{D_A} \right| \times 100 \quad (9)$$

$$(\text{MAE}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\Delta_i| \quad (10)$$

$$(\text{MSE}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\Delta_i)^2 \quad (11)$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\Delta_i)^2} \quad (12)$$

where D_A is an actual distance and D_M is a measurement distance.

To assess the performance, two scenarios are employed. In the first, objects (license plates) are utilized that are equally far from the camera, whereas, in the second, objects of different classes that are relatively far away (1 m) are employed. It was also evaluated at different separations between the camera and the detected multi-class objects.

Figure 8. License Plates are Examples of Objects that are Equally Far from the Camera

Two model automobiles' license plates were positioned so they were at the same distance from the camera. Two model cars' license plates were measured manually at a distance of 4.3 meters. The relative error of the distance estimate algorithm is 2.0%. This is what Figure 8 shows. The results of the distance estimation for the same class with an RMSE 3.5 score are shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Evaluation Metrics for the Same Class (License Plate)

Class	Actual Distance(m)	Estimated Distance(m)	Absolute Error	Relative Error (%)
License-plate	4.3	4.387	0.087	2.0
	6.3	6.016	0.284	4.5
RMSE = 3.5				

In this test scenario, the algorithm produces very good results.

Because YOLO produces extremely accurate border boxes, its distance estimation is quite good.

Figure 9. The Result of Multi-Class Distance Estimation at Different Distances

Figure 9 shows the results of the multi-class distance estimate (c), (d), (e), and (f), as well as the distance estimation for the license plate utilizing two model cars at different distances (a) and (b). The measurement results, which represent the actual distance (in meters) when the camera lens algorithm was used, are provided in the following tables. Two model automobiles were positioned so that one was nearer the cameras than the other. The distance estimation results for the car license plate with an RMSE 3.12 score are shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Evaluation Metrics for License Plates at Different Distances

Actual Distance(m)	Estimated Distance(m)	Absolute Error	Relative Error (%)
5	4.940	0.06	1.20
6	6.038	0.038	0.63
6.5	6.393	0.107	1.65
7	6.580	0.42	6.00
8	7.799	0.201	2.50
9	9.057	0.057	0.63
9.5	9.155	0.345	3.60
10	9.871	0.129	1.29
11	10.427	0.573	5.20
12	11.698	0.302	2.50
13	12.386	0.614	4.72
14	14.028	0.028	0.20
RMSE = 3.12			

The approximate distance between the license plate and the camera is measured at regular intervals.

Table 3 displays the results. Table 3 shows that the accuracy of the method is less than 4.7% up to 13 meters but significantly drops beyond that point. Table 4 below displays the results of the license plate distance estimation with an RMSE of 2.3.

According to Tables 3 and 4, the license plate distance estimation has a higher RMSE score than the motorcycle distance estimation. The multi-class objects in the trained dataset failed to predict efficiently when predicting an object at a distance of 15 meters.

Table 4 Evaluation Metrics for the Motorcycle Class of the Trained Dataset

Actual Distance(m)	Estimated Distance(m)	Absolute Error	Relative Error (%)
3.5	3.594	0.094	2.6
4.5	4.574	0.074	1.6
5.5	5.509	0.009	0.16
6.5	6.343	0.157	2.4
7.5	7.25	0.25	3.33
RMSE = 2.3			

Where the distances between identified objects and cameras were less than 15 meters, the experiment's results showed that the YOLOv8n algorithm, in conjunction with the camera lens approach, produced dependable and highly effective results.

Conclusion

The technique for calculating the distances between objects and cameras was presented in this paper. Beginning with the YOLOv8n technique, the suggested method finds multi-class objects in the input image. From the positions and bounding boxes of the identified objects, a total of four

features are then retrieved. By applying the camera's "Lens principle," these characteristics are utilized to calculate the separations between the objects and the camera. For vehicle detection, YOLOv8n is among the most effective models. At 30 frames per second, the YOLOv8n model has achieved 85% precision and 62% recall.

After testing, the system demonstrated 84% detection accuracy and an average distance estimation error of less than 4.7% out of 13 meters. Thus, it can be concluded that the suggested technology is suitable for uses like automated driving.

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